

Perceived Psycho-Physical Factors Enhancing Sex-For-Grade In Higher Institutions In Nigeria

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Abstract

Sexual harassment has been a recent problem bedeviling the sub-sector of higher institutions in Nigeria. It has diluted the educational quality where sex-for-grade has become a norm and on the increase. Therefore, this study sought to assess the perceived psycho-physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. The study adopted a descriptive survey research design, and the study was conducted at the Federal University Otuoke. Upon A sample of 1000 respondents consisting of both lecturers and students which was selected through stratified random sampling technique. The study obtained its data through a validated instrument. Data was analyzed with Graph Pad Prism 5 statistical software. Results showed perceived physical factors having 3.98 ± 1.20 with 80% extent of perception and psychological factors have 3.83 ± 1.36 with 76% rate of perception. The study observed that there was no significant different between mean response of students and lecturers on the perceived psycho-physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade at $P < .05$. The study concludes that both students and lecturers perceived that there are physical and psychological factors enhancing sex-for-grade in Higher Institutions in Nigeria. Therefore, the researchers recommend that government should increase institutional funding to provide physical facilities that will reduce or eliminate sex-for-grade in higher institutions.

Key words: Physical factors, psychological factors, sex-for-grade, examination, hard courses, enhancing, and perceived.

Introduction

Federal Republic of Nigeria (FRN) (2004) has given a policy framework for quality Education. This becomes imperative because education is seen as an instrument per excellence for National Development. The products produced by the institutions determine the multi-dimensional development of any state or country. Academic success is a fundamental goal for all tertiary institutions. However, the educational institutions in Nigeria have been subjected to criticism as people began to doubt the quality of graduates and their certificate upon graduation, it is a known fact that there is the existence of malpractices such as sorting of lecturers and examination officers and other sort forms of lobbying and stealing in examination halls (Queensoap & Memory, 2013). More recently the extent of malpractice in higher institutions has taken different dimensions through sex - for- grade.

The increasing rate of sex for grade in Nigerian institutions of higher learning is a problem of considerable magnitude. It is an ethical and a human rights issue that has implications not only for the quality and integrity of the educational system, but also for the physical, mental and social well-being of its victims. It is an issue that should be taken seriously due to the gravity of the physical, psychological, academic, social and legal implications it may have.

Sex-for-grade can be said includes having sexual relationship with the opposite sex in exchange for good grades. Sex-for-grade can be interchangeably called sexual harassment. The only difference is that while sexual harassment is a general word for sexually abusive act in any area of life, whether religion, public or private sectors. Sex-for-grade is mainly an illicit affair between students and their tutors. The University of Iowa (1991) considers sexual harassment as the direct or implied threats that submission to sexual advances may favourably affect promotion, grades or letters of recommendation or that rejection of sexual advances may produce a negative effect; direct proposition of a sexual nature; subtle pressure for a sexual action, one element of which may be a conduct such as repeated staring, conduct that tends to bring discomfort or humiliation to a reasonable person at whom the conduct was directed. These may include unnecessary touching, patting, hugging or brushing against a person's clothing or body or remarks about sexual activity or speculation about sexual experience.

This implies that sex-for-grade can be described as when lecturers dangle promises of good grades or upgrading poor grades for sexual intimacy. Smart (2023) asserted that Sex-for-grade is a deeply entrenched problem that involves educators exploiting their power over students in exchange for sexual favours. In every open social institution where there are males and females, there is bound to be interaction among them, and such interaction could either be positive or negative. Sexual harassment could therefore be a product of such negative interaction among males and females, which may have far-reaching implications for individuals and the nation at large (Smart, 2023).

Universities all over the world are expected to provide an ideal environment for the pursuit of scholarship (learning, teaching and research) and such a provision assumes that male and female members of the academia have equal rights and protection under the law establishing the institutions. However there have been incessant complaints about unfair treatment meted to students in their pursuit of learning and other sundry issues.

One area of concern is the complaint made by some female students who are embarrassed by demands of sex or other sexual favours by lecturers. Allegations of sexual harassment by male professors are so prevalent in Nigerian universities that many female students claim to either have been either sexually abused by their lecturers or to know someone who has experienced it (Daikpor, 2021).

On the other hand, some male lecturers are also embarrassed by pestering advances made to them by female students in exchange for good grades and marks. This was observed in (Udechukwu et al., 2020) stating that there are female students who intend to succumb to sex-for-grades that use the instrumentality of subtle urging, loitering round the concerned lecturer, dressing half nude, constant visitation to his office, text messages, gifts, and suggestive but giving seemingly innocent

statement with multiple interpretations. The problem of sex-for-grade is no longer a one-sided issue, though more emphasis is on male lecturers who became vulnerable to harassing female students. According to Ibrahim et al. (2020), several male lecturers had confirmed, in their study, that they had been sexually propositioned by female lecturers.

Incidents of sexual harassment have been reported in Universities, Colleges of Education and Polytechnics. It is obvious that this paper might not present the rate of prevalence of sex-for-grade in Nigerian higher institutions. Nevertheless, it is on record that some Professors and academic staff had been indicted by one disciplinary panel or the other, for awarding grades for sex; and subsequently suspended by the school authorities. For instance, (Achema, 1992) reported that there was a case in which one Caroline Okojie dragged her supervisor, who is a Professor, to court for refusing to approve her thesis for the Part 11 Fellowship of West African Postgraduate Medical College until he had carnal knowledge of her. The court eventually ruled in her favour.

The issue of sexual harassment or sex-for-grade is something that appears on the headlines of papers. Recently, (Ogugua, 2024) reported a case of sexual harassment that had been on the Independent Corrupt Practices and other Related Offences Commission (ICPC). In the report, it was told that some nude pictures and videos of certain contacts (who were students of the accused) were found in his phone when his WhatsApp messaging application was subjected to forensic examination. (Fadipe & Bakenne, 2020) affirmed that studies have already acknowledged sexual scandals as public relations nightmares of higher learning institutions. They discovered that the institutions mostly used denial with diminished response strategy to blame societal decadence and vulnerable female students for downplaying the severity of sexual harassment incidence by the institutions. However, it was observed that female students feel aggrieved that school administrations and the national government neglected them for failing to outlaw sexual harassment and severely punish offenders (Fadipe & Bakenne, 2020). This act of sex-for-grade can be enhanced by certain factors which may be relative from institution to institutions.

Moreover, it has been observed that some courses are perceived by students as not being easy to pass, it is a known fact that in Federal University Otuoke, for instance, during the final year, many students still sit for G.S103 (Natural Science), G.S105 and G.S101 to mention but a few of the almighty scarring courses. During inception, students are erroneously made to believe that these courses are never passed like other courses. This, then make the students "go an extra mile" by either cheating to pass or adopt all sorts of tricks to lure male lecturers into having intimate affairs with them as a reward for passing these courses. According to Ursua, (1994), female students in the discipline of science are constantly under intense sexual pressure from their male classmates and lecturers. This, to an extent may account for low enrollments and high dropout rates of female students from their studies. It has also been noted that maturity and academic levels of students are considered as critical factors in sexual harassment.

Currently, students now come in as young as age 16 or 15. It is on record that the Minister of Education, Tahir Mamman when assessing the conduct of 2024 Unified Tertiary Matriculation Examination (UTME) in Abuja "earlier stated that the minimum age for admission into Nigerian

higher institutions is 18” (Kenechi, 2024). Professor Mamman had expressed concerned that parents are pressuring their wards at ages 15 and 16 to gain admission into tertiary institutions. It is obvious that many of them are leaving the tutelage of their homes for the first time and when they come into school and see that they are not accountable to anyone, they may have a sense of freedom to do whatever they want. Some lecturers may take advantage of their naivety and make them believe that lecturers are the powers that be.

Mode of dressing is another social incidence that has been linked to sexual harassment in universities. According to (Ogah, 2004) there is no specific dress code in some universities in Nigeria. As a result of this, students who feel that one must dress to belong, dress provocatively and in alluring outfit to lecturers’ offices. The way most girls dress is so embarrassing that many men find it difficult to concentrate on their academic responsibilities. This indecency in dressing is so much now that many Nigerian universities had started combating it, remarked Ogohi (2005). It is true that universities like Federal University Otuoke had introduced dress codes committee and students who are not decently dressed are not allowed into the school premises and may not be attended to in offices. Some institutions of higher learning are more like business centers than ivory towers. Some university administrations seem to be careless on how their students present themselves which had triggered sex-for-grade and its related sexual harassments.

Furthermore, Ibrahim et al. (2020) observed the following as some causes of sex for grade in Nigerian tertiary institutions. these were **lecturer-centered** which include lack of self-discipline, inability to control sexual urge, poor remuneration of academics, single individual course instructors and unwieldy powers of lecturers over courses; **student-centered** that consist of drug influence, deliberate use of sex by some female students as weapon for academic rewards, economic gains, indecent dressing, causal familiarization with lecturers and fun; and **institutional** which consisted of lack of clear and transparent procedures for complaints and addressing sexual harassment issues, etc. The study affirmed that 50% of students and 45% academic lecturers at various Nigerian tertiary institutions confirmed that there is no clear procedure for reporting sexual harassment issues, Ibrahim et al. (2020) reiterated.

This trend becomes increasingly disturbing to the extent of turning higher institutions as vulnerable to sex-for-grade. It, therefore, becomes a worrisome academic matter to empirically investigate some perceived factors promoting sex for grade in higher institutions which will help in no little way to make viable recommendations for policy actions. Thus, this study was to assess the perceived psycho-physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria.

Methods

The design adopted for this study was a descriptive survey research design. Students and academic staff of the Federal University Otuoke formed the target population of the study. A proportionate stratified sampling technique was used to select 860 students and 140 academic staff from the Faculties of Science, Engineering, Education and Management Science. A self-designed instrument titled: “Questionnaire on Factors Enhancing sex-for-grade”(QFES) was used to elicit

information from respondents. The study instrument (QFES) contained eleven (11) items with a five-point rating scale in the modified Likert Format. That is, having response level such as Strongly Agree, Agree, and Undecided, Disagree and strongly disagree with rating 5,4,3,2 and 1 respectively. The researchers validated the instrument of the study through face and content validity methods. The researchers adopted a test-retest method of reliability which on analysis of the data from the double administration with Pearson moment correlation gave a reliability coefficient of 0.78. This value was high enough to consider the study instrument reliable. The instrument was administered by face-to-face method through four research assistants. Tables and sample percentage were used to present the demographic information of respondents while mean and standard deviation were used to analyze data to give answers to the research questions. Meanwhile, t-test was used to test the two hypotheses at 0.05 level of error probability.

Results

Presentation of Respondents’ Demographic Information

Table 1

Distribution of Respondents’ Demographic Information

S/N	VARIABLES	FREQUENCY (N=1000)	PERCENTAGE %
1	GENDER		
	Male	520	52
	Female	480	48
2	AGE (YEARS)		
	15-20	110	11
	21-25	380	38
	26-30	280	28
	31-34	80	8
	35 and above	150	15
3	MARITAL STATUS		
	Single	820	82
	Married	180	18
4	NAME OF FACULTY		
	Science	330	33
	Education	220	22
	Engineering	210	21
	Management science	220	22
5	CATEGORY OF RESPONDENTS		
	Lecturers	140	14
	Students	860	86

Source: Research Field work, 2021

Table 1 showed that out of 1000, male has 52% while females consist of 48% implying that more males than female formed the sample of the study. For age, 15-20 years forms 11%, 21-25 has 38%, 26-30 is 28%, and 31-34 is 8% and 35 and above has 15% indicating that age bracket 21-25 formed the majority of respondents. Table 1 showed that there was 82% single and 18% married. This means that there were more singles that were involved in the study. Meanwhile, the

distribution of the respondents by faculty indicates that more respondents were made to be involved in the study showing that science is 33%, education with management science is 22% each while engineering faculty has 21%. Also, the distribution by category of respondents indicates that 14% of lecturers that participated in the study while 82% was all students implying more students than lecturers.

Research Question 1: What are the perceived physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria?

Table 2
Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation

S/N	STATEMENTS	N	X	STD	X%	CM	REMARK
1	inadequate hostel accommodation	1000	4.42	1.11	88	3.0	Accepted
2	inadequate classroom facilities	1000	3.97	1.01	79		Accepted
3	poor technological advancement	1000	3.85	1.19	77		Accepted
4	lack of office space for lecturers	1000	4.03	1.31	81		Accepted
5	absence of adequate library facility	1000	3.65	1.37	73		Accepted
	Grand N/X/STD/X%	1000	3.98	1.20	80		Accepted

Source: Research Field work, 2021

Table 2 shows respondents' perception regarding physical factors enhancing Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. It was observed in table 2 that inadequate hostel accommodation has 4.42±1.11 mean and standard deviation with 88% very high perception rate, inadequate classroom facilities have 3.97±1.01 mean and standard deviation with 79% high perception rate, poor technological advancement has 3.85±1.19 with 77% high perception rate, lack of office space for lecturers has 4.03±1.31 with 81% very high perception while absence of adequate library facility has 3.65±1.37 with 73% high perception rate. Meanwhile, the grand mean/standard with mean percentage is 3.98±1.20 with 80% which was greater than the criterion mean (3.0), indicating that respondents highly perceived that the investigated physical factors enhance Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions.

Research Question 2: What are the perceived psychological factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria?

Table 3
Summary of Mean and Standard Deviation

S/N	STATEMENTS	N	X	STD	X%	CM	REMARK
6	fear of lecturers handling scared courses	1000	4.32	1.25	86	3.0	Accepted
7	response set towards a particular course	1000	3.58	1.44	72		Accepted
8	depraved value system in Nigeria	1000	3.63	1.43	73		Accepted
9	threats from lecturers	1000	4.23	1.20	86		Accepted
10	academic level of students	1000	3.67	1.41	73		Accepted

11	maturity of the student	1000	3.39	1.43	68	Accepted
	Grand N/X/STD/X%	1000	3.83	1.36	76	Accepted

Source: Research Field work, 2021

Table 3 shows respondents' perception regarding psychological factors enhancing Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. It was observed in table 3 that fear of lecturers handling scared courses has 4.32 ± 1.25 mean and standard deviation with 86% very high perception rate, response set towards a particular course has 3.58 ± 1.44 mean and standard deviation with 72% high perception rate, depraved value system in Nigeria has 3.63 ± 1.43 with 73% high perception rate, threats from lecturers has 4.23 ± 1.20 with 86% very high perception, academic level of students has 3.67 ± 1.41 with 73% high perception rate while maturity of the student has 3.39 ± 1.43 with 68% high perception rate. Meanwhile, the grand mean/standard with mean percentage is 3.83 ± 1.36 with 76% which was greater than the criterion mean (3.0), indicating that respondents highly perceived that the investigated psychological factors enhance Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions.

Null Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria.

Table 4

Summary of t-test Statistics

Comparing Pairs	N	X	STD	t-ratio	Do	P val.	Decision
Students vs. Lecturers	860	20.27	3.27	0.4793	998	0.6328	Ho accepted (ns) at 0.05

Source: Research Field Work

It can be discerned from table 4 that for the number of students (N) is 860 and the students' group has mean (X) and standard deviation (STD) of 20.27 ± 3.27 . For lecturers, Number participated (N) is 140, mean with standard deviation are 20.71 ± 3.00 . While the t-ratio is 0.4793, degree of freedom (DF) is 998, P value is 0.6328 at P value of 0.05, that is, $P > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions is accepted. This means that both lecturers and students perceived in the same way that the physical factors under investigation enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions.

4.1.7 Null Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived psychological factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria

Table 5: Summary of t-test Statistics

Comparing Pairs	N	X	STD	t-ratio	Df	P val.	Decision
Students vs. Lecturers	860	24.07	3.87	0.0014	998	0.9983	Ho accepted (ns) at 0.05

Source: Research Field Work

It can be discerned from table 5 that for the number of students (N) is 860 and the students' group has mean (X) and standard deviation (STD) of 24.07 ± 3.87 . For lecturers, Number participated (N) is 140, mean with standard deviation are 24.07 ± 5.69 . While the t-ratio is 0.0014, degree of freedom (DF) is 998, P value is 0.9983 at *P value of 0.05*, that is, $P > 0.05$. Thus, the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived psychological factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions is accepted. This means that both lecturers and students perceived in the same way that the psychological factors under investigation enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions.

Discussion

This study was purposed to assess perceived psycho-physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institution in Nigeria. The study selected 1000 participants from the students' folk (86%) and lecturers (14%). It was observed in this study that inadequate hostel accommodation, inadequate classroom facilities, poor technological advancement, lack of office space for lecturers and absence of adequate library facility are perceived as physical factors capable of enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions. This was established by the respondents' grand mean/standard deviation with mean percentage of 3.98 ± 1.20 with 80%. This suggests that lecturers and students have perceived physical factors at a very high percentage and level of agreement.

The study further determined that the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived physical factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions is accepted. This means that both lecturers and students perceived in the same way that the physical factors under investigation enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions. Also due to the ways, which the affairs of some institution are run, students are made to surface untold hardship. Results are not released when they should, hostel accommodation does not go round, the classrooms are not adequate and even some lecturers do not have offices. These encourage sexual harassment because students are made to be at the mercy of anyone who promises to help.

This current study discovered that fear of lecturers handling scared courses such as mathematically oriented courses, science based, etc., response set towards a particular course, depraved value system in Nigeria, threats from lecturers, academic level of students and maturity of the student are rated at a high perception as psychological factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. This position is evidenced in the grand mean/standard with mean percentage of 3.83 ± 1.36 with 76% which was greater than the criterion mean (3.0), indicating that respondents highly perceived that the investigated psychological factors enhance Sex-for-Grade in higher institutions.

To collaborate this descriptive point of view, the result of the inferential statistics shown that the null hypothesis of no significant difference between mean response of lecturers and students on perceived psychological factors enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions is accepted. This means that both lecturers and students perceived in the same way that the psychological factors under investigation enhance sex-for-grade in higher institutions. This finding was supported by the

work of Ursua, (1994) and Ibrahim et al. (2020). In their different works it was observed that there are certain psychological factors such as lack of inability to control sexual urge, unwieldy power of a lecturer over a course, etc. are capable to push students into sex-for-grade.

Conclusion

Based on the findings of the study, the researchers concludes that physical factors such as inadequate hostel accommodation, inadequate classroom facilities, poor technological advancement, lack of office space for lecturers and absence of adequate library facility are capable of enhancing sex-for-grade in higher institutions. Similarly psychological factors such as maturity of students, fear of powerful lecturers handling hard courses, depraved value system, etc. can promote sex-for-grade in higher institutions in Nigeria. The study concludes also that students and lecturers perceived factors promoting sex-for-grade in Nigerian Universities in the same way.

Recommendations

Following the findings and conclusion of this current study, the researchers proffer the following recommendations.

- Government should increase institution funding to provide physical facilities that will reduce or eliminate sex-for-grade in higher institutions
- Guidance and Counseling services should be made functional on university campuses to guide students on difficult courses.
- Non-governmental organizations should carry out mobilization, enlightenment, and advocacy on ills of sex-for-grade among universities.

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